
COLLECTION DEVELOPMENT IN INDUSTRY LIBRARY : JAIN IRRIGATION SYSTEM LTD.

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Abstract-

This research paper shows about Collection Development in Industry Library special case of Library of Jain Irrigation System Ltd. In this research paper study the Role of Industry Library, its research methodology, Collection Development in Industry Library, Scope, Limitation and Conclusion etc.

Keyword- *Collection Development, Industrial Library, IFLA*

Introduction –

Library collection development is the process of meeting the information needs of the people (a service population) in a timely and economical manner using information resources locally held, as well as from other organizations.

According to the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), acquisition and collection development focuses on methodological and topical themes pertaining to acquisition of print and other analogue library materials (by purchase, exchange, gift, legal deposit), and the licensing and purchase of electronic information resources.

Role of Industrial Library :-

Gordon saker observation that large volume of information is lost because of major part industry is not able to organize it. He also emphasized the need for the specialized skill and experience both in collection and distribution keep the scientist and technicians abstract of the latest technical information. Biographical scatter create many problem in locating necessary information leading to waste of time effort of user it is one of the reason to have trained librarian capable of disseminating of right information to right person right time at right cost so that by information user and not burdened with unnecessary reading worthless information feature of industrial library.

- 1) To acquire and organize document and more important information they content a structure form so as to regularize its retrieval the library also provide expertise in handling information its storage retrieval and exploitation.
- 2) Information delight by industrial library into broad subject categories of scientific and technical information business and economical information and finance, personal legal information.
- 3) To save the time and money by avoiding duplication and to enable to staff to exploit the information provided industrial user: Industrial library serves limited and well defined client and limited to its organization. The client range from employees of single department throughout the organization. Industrial user can group either by the there professional function area or there job level.
- 4) Employees, scientist engineers and non technical person.
- 5) Technical qualified person in technical assignment.
- 6) Technical qualified person in non-technical assignment.
- 7) Non technical qualified person in technical.

Research Methodology:

Case Study –

In case study method aims at studying everything about something rather than something rather than

something about everything. The purpose of case study is to study deep and detailed of the unit of this project case. Study use in that study of all thing. A case study aims at studying everything about everything as in the case of a statistical method.

a) Questionnaire :For this project we use the questionnaire method in this method a questionnaire sent to the person concerned with the request of question written in questionnaire. This method is very useful for the project. We get all information through questionnaire. A questionnaire is essentially a skill transaction of objectives into a set of question intended of be answered in written in this questionnaire the question is arranged in this way that we get all information about the project /library.

b) Observation by self : Observation means viewing and seeing we go on observation something or other while we awake most of such observation for this project we also use observation method in that method we observe the information. Observation may be defined as a systematic viewing of specific phenomenon in its proper setting for the specific purpose of gathering data includes both ‘seeing’ and ‘hearing’.

Collection Development in Industrial library :

Collection is the recorded knowledge in the journals, report, microfilm, cassettes, floppy disk and other from collected for use in a library. All library activities and services are based on these collection.

‘Collection development’ is the term widely used synonymously with term ‘selection’ and acquisition’. It is the planned systematic development of a collection in library. It is process of linking all the decision of the management to the provision of recorded knowledge to the user community on the basis of their needs.

Collection development involves a number of activities by which a library acquires materials of all types needs to the users. It is a dynamic and continuous activity to develop a need up -to -date and balanced collection fit to meet the document and information need of users.

The process of collection development comprises the:

- 1) Collection and analysis of information / document need of users.
- 2) Scientific selection of materials to meet the library objectives.
- 3) Planned acquisition of a balanced collection.
- 4) Regular evaluation of a collection.
- 5) Proper maintenance of the collection.
- 6) Proper utilization of book fund.

An attempt is made to evaluate the selection procedure, acquisition methods, quality and size of collection, its updating, allocation of book funds role librarian in collection development users satisfaction.

• REVIEW OF LITERATURE :-

In this section attempt is made to review briefly the previous research and literatures libraries. The review does not claim to be comprehensive since it was not possible to narrate all works no the subject within the limitations of the present research.

• Webstar New 20th Century Dictionary (1978) defines the various term of Industry. In that define characteristics of industry, Working of Industries and Use of Industry.

• (Uddhav R. Jadhav 2010) provides a comprehensive information about resources,, infrastructure, services offered by the information resource centres. The professional looking after the centres are trying to cope up with the before the Library and Information Science Profession. In that included that, History of Special Libraries including industrial libraries in India and Maharashtra ;

• Thaulingon N (2000). Industrial library surveys in the Indian context are also covered because they not only contain much valuable information but also due to the fact that they are the available studies reported in the literature.

JAIN IRRIGATION SYSTEM LTD., LIBRARY :-

The library is important part of industries. It is useful for his special purpose and for special user it. The libraries of industries libraries of Research association & Societies the libraries of technical and Scientific research units belongs.

Library of Jain Irrigation System Ltd., one of types special library. Jain Irrigation System Ltd., Library includes three libraries. Main central library Jain valley and Jain hills (JHL) / (JVL)

JAIN VALLEY :-This library was established in 1997. This whole activities and operation of this library under the supervision of Mr. Sammer Sharma (Manager, HRD) with his one assistant. This main objective of this industry is to production of dehydrated onion powder and purees at other side the main objective of this library is to assets the associates by providing latest and complete knowledge regarding production, this is provided by its management. The budget and expenditure of Library is near about 50000 to 80000 per year. This library have good collection of books in English language on various subject, which are 2087 books. The whole book collection emphasis on food technology while this library subscribe the 79 types of periodical. This library has also good collection of non - book material. This library provides the service to the employee of his parent organization that are 242 in numbers.

AIM OF OBJECTIVES :-

- 1) To on historical background of institutes and its activities.
- 2) To study the role of library in various projects and publications.
- 3) To study the collection and development of the library.
- 4) To study the library services thoroughly.
- 5) To study the collection of non-book material.

SCOPE OF STUDY :-

- 1) The Present study include only for industrial library.
- 2) The study shall through on the present condition of special.
- 3) The study the present the organizational services and special libraries.

LIMITATION :-

The present investigation deal with the comparative study of industrial library. This study is limited to Jain irrigation Library.

Jain Irrigation – A brief Introduction-

Jain Irrigation Systems Ltd is a diversified entity with a turnover in excess of Rs. 3000 crores. Jain have a Global presence with 20 manufacturing bases spread over 5 continents. Our products are supplied to 110 countries with able assistance from 3000 Dealers and distributors worldwide.

Jain Irrigation is the 2nd largest Micro-Irrigation company in the world. The micro-irrigation Division manufactures full range of precision-irrigation products; provides services from soil survey, engineering design to agronomic support, nurtures two sprawling 1500-acre R & D and technology demonstration farms and Hi-Tech Agri Institute houses a full-fledged Training & Extension Centre and undertakes turnkey projects for agricultural and irrigation development in toto. Over 1000 agri and irrigation scientists, engineers, technologist and technicians are engaged in offering consultancy for complete or partial project planning and implementation like Watershed Development through Wasteland Transformation, including crop selection and rotation.

We are also the largest plastic pipe manufacturer in India covering a wide range of pipes and fittings. We annually process over 200,000 MT of various polymers. We extrude and injection mould PVC, PE, PP along with other engineering polymers like Polycarbonate, Polyamide, PBT, ABS etc. we are a Total

Solution Provider for various thermoplastic piping systems that are used in transportation/conveyance of water and other fluids, semi-solids, gases and cables.

The Tissue Culture Division products Grands Naine Banana plantlets and has established matching primary and secondary hardening facilities as well as independent R & D and virology labs for pre & post production quality control. Similarly a modern Biotech lab equipped with PCR based and other molecular markers, HPLC ,AAS& GC has been established to meet the needs of continuous of onion, mango and some of the energy crops.

Jain irrigation is a Total Agri-Solution provider from end to end; concept to commissioning. It is through such multidimensional activity profile that we nurture the complete agri value chain and have become a one-stop hi-tech agri shop. The reward has been a million satisfied farmers and scores of happy customers globally.

SUBJECTWISE COLLECTION OF BOOK

Sr. no	Subject	96-97	97-98	98-99	99-00	00-01	01-02	02-03	03-04	04-05	05-06
1	Management	26	34	20	74	17	30	26	27	70	80
2	Irrigation	81	66	74	95	49	132	221	111	122	112
3	Water	133	23	25	31	21	22	52	51	65	70
4	Agriculture	61	43	35	25	16	22	89	90	235	230
5	Law	34	28	32	45	13	24	70	56	65	62
6	Dictionary	26	21	36	22	11	19	35	25	32	35
7	Food	33	18	18	43	13	15	61	50	56	52
8	Plastic	18	23	18	44	25	2	59	65	59	63
9	Religion	136	120	140	206	118	63	81	71	92	82
10	General	428	376	398	585	283	329	694	86	142	150

There are large books available on agriculture and management. There are little books available on Marathi. The language of most books is English. The total collection of book more than 5000.

PERIODICAL COLLECTION

Sr. no	Subject	96-97	97-98	98-99	99-00	2000-2001	2001-2002	2002-2003	2003-2004	2004-2005	2005-2006
1	National	142	139	130	120	125	100	102	101	98	98
2	International	24	23	22	27	20	16	20	23	26	28

SUBJECT WISE COLLECTION OF NON – BOOK MATERIAL

Sr. no	Subject	96-97	97-98	98-99	99-00	2000-2001	2001-2002	2002-2003	2003-2004	2004-2005	2005-2006
1	Audio / Video	70	80	75	74	70	60	40	65	45	56
2	CD	30	40	70	85	91	90
3	Other material	20	28	26	42	18	18	14	11	16	13
	Total	90	108	101	116	118	118	124	161	152	159

Conclusion :

Industrial library with technology may affect the librarians. Technological may affect the librarians. Technological advances suggest that nature of library operation and possibly the role of libraries may change with use of new technical equipment in library like computerization of library. The work is made easy and

correct with technology. The most use of Industrial Library is found in getting advance knowledge to the persons work in industry.

Jain Irrigation System Ltd. Jalgaon have (645) publications during the last five years i.e. from 2007-2011. It was found that in eighteen (47.36%) libraries users are generating information in various disciplines. Researcher feels that it is a good indication of the information services provided to them.

Average number of users availing facilities of industrial library under survey ranging from 100 to 200 R & D personnel, managers and technical people were found major users of the industrial libraries. Average 500 users per industry are using the services provided by industrial libraries. It was found that seventeen (44.73%) industrial libraries are conducting user orientation programmes which will promote the use of resources and services provided for them.

The collection acquired in the Jain Irrigation industrial libraries is stored in steel or wooden book cases. Steel furniture was found popular among libraries. Popularity of using PVC furniture was also found increasing slowly. Most of the libraries are having their own equipments for day to day library work.

It was also found that some of the costly equipments are shared with organization on resource sharing basis or common facility.

Total number of employees in different organization was found ranging from 500 to 2000. Fifty percent of the organization are having average 500 staff in their organizations. This includes workers who do not use the library. Industries having their works at different places and marketing offices in metropolitan cities employed workers and staff unable to use the library services due to geographical distance. Most of the industries are having their works at different places. However, the libraries are located at one place only as a central library. It was found that 23 libraries were manned by professionally qualified libraries. Numbers of staff in the library ranges from 1 to 6 average ratio of the professional to non- professional was found 1 :1 as compared to female.

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